

The Effect of Using Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) on the Reading Comprehension of Expository Texts for the Iranian University Female Senior

MAJID FARDY¹, LIDA NAMDAR¹, SOGHRA FARHADI¹, HOSSEIN NOORI SHORABI¹, ABOLFAZL SABOORI¹

¹ISLAMIC AZAD UNIVERSITY-KHODABANDEH BRANCH

Abstract:

This study aimed to explore the effect of computer-assisted Language Learning (CALL) on the reading comprehension of expository texts of Iranian female senior. The study was designed as a true-experimental research- Randomized Control Experimental Group, Pre-test-Post-test Design. The subjects in this study were 60 female senior from Islamic Azad University of Khodabandeh who are studying English as their major course. They were senior who had been selected out of many other EFL students through the Standardized Nelson Test. These subjects were divided into two groups, control group and experimental group. The experimental group was taught using computer-assisted instructions in a language laboratory, while subjects in the control group were taught using a traditional method of instructions in traditional classroom setting. The training took 12 sessions and the same instructor taught the groups three hours each session. During the first week, a pre-test was given to both groups. Then, a post-test was given at the end of the instructions. An independent sample t-test appeared to be an appropriate tool for data analysis in this study since there were two groups who were evaluated twice through pre and posttest. The results showed that there were statistically significant differences between two groups that can be attributed to the effect of CALL on the reading comprehension of expository texts.

KeyWords: Computer-assisted Language Learning, Expository Text, Traditional Method

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Few teachers nowadays, at least in the Western world, rely solely on chalk and blackboard. Over the years, more and more technical inventions have taken their place among the educational aids with which teachers surround themselves, to make their teaching more effective. What distinguishes the computers from other pieces of equipment, such as tape recorders and film projectors, and what forms in fact the basis of its being an educational aid is its interactive capability (Nelson Ward & Kaplow 1976).

Significant use of CALL began in the 1960s. Since then, the development of CALL software has followed the changes in teaching methodologies (Han 1996). As teaching method changed to audio-lingual and communicative approaches, CALL software included simulations and more interactive programs. Research has shown that learning strategies employed in CALL can affect

the quality of learning the language. However, it still lacks methods and a clear theoretical foundation (Christopher 1995).

The idea of using computers for teaching purposes in subjects like modern languages arouses mixed feeling and meets with a variety of reactions (Kenning & Kenning 1983). The fact that computers are used in the teaching of other subjects and are put to a great many applications in society makes one suspect that no field lays completely outside their scope and that they might indeed be of some use (Davies & Higgins 1980). To many, the prospect of using computers is not without appeal; it is the kind of challenge which one feels drawn to respond to. At the same time, the technology frightens us; we are afraid that it may come to dominate us and we may be even being afraid of losing our jobs.

Kulik and Kulik(1991) surveyed more than 500 studies which compared learners who received computer-assisted instruction with the learners who received traditional instruction. They found that learners tend to learn more and in less time with computer-assisted learning.

There are two questions that this research is going to answer:

- Is there a statistically significant difference concerning the gain scores on the reading comprehension of expository texts between the learners instructed by the CALL and the learners instructed by the traditional approach?
- What do the language learners in the experimental group think about the CALL as to learn?

II. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Subjects

The students in this study were sixty university female senior in Khodabandeh Islamic Azad university (educational year 2011) studying English as a foreign Language, with ages between 22and 26. They were Iranian students. They consented to participate in this study and were motivated by being informed in advance that they would receive extra credit for their participation.

2.2. Instrument

For the purpose of the study and to investigate the hypotheses, several instruments were utilized. They were validated through a pilot study before being employed in the project. The instruments applied were:

First, the Standardized Nelson English Language Test including 64 multiple-choice items (version 260B, 1976) along with an answer sheet was used to homogenize the subjects. In other words, the subjects were exposed to the Standardized Nelson English Language Test and those students who acquired more than seventy percent of the scores were selected for the main purpose of the study. The selected subjects were divided into two groups, control group and experimental group. Each group consisted of 30 female subjects.

A structured interview guide (based on a journal for teachers of English by Campion on the Internet) was used to collect data to answers the second research question. The subjects in the experimental group were interviewed one by one regarding their opinions about the CALL. The interview took place in the Islamic Azad University of Khodabandeh without a time limit, but took approximately 7-10 minutes for each subject. The interviews with the learners were tape-recorded and the researcher took notes. The subjects were interviewed in English.

Computer-assisted language learning, as defined for this study, was provided in a language laboratory where learners worked alone on a computer using the provided programs and learnt at their own pace. The instructor did not participate in the learning process, but he made sure that learners were working alone on their computers. On the other hand, traditional instruction was given in the lecture format as information going from the instructor to the learners. Subjects had to follow the instructor's schedule and they could not learn at their own pace. All the materials used in the groups were identical. For classroom practice, *TOEFL* (2002) reading comprehension intermediate levels were used. The learners instructed by CALL used the CD versions of these materials.

2.3. Design

Since real random selection of the subjects was possible, the study followed the True-Experimental Design with the help of pre-test, post-test pattern. The diagram of such a design is as follows (Ary 1996). (See Table I)

TABLE I
RANDOMIZED CONTROL EXPERIMENTAL GROUP, PRE-TEST POST-TEST DESIGN

Group	Pre-test	Independent variable	Post-test
A	T1	X	T2
B	T1	-	T2

In this design T1 (A) and T1 (B) are the tests before applying the treatment, and T2 (A) , T2 (B) are the tests after treatment, respectively, where X is the treatment. Based on the design the difference between the mean of the pretest and posttest of the first group scores and the difference between the mean of the pretest and posttest for the next group scores are tested for the statistical significance. At the outset of the study two groups were given a pre-test described in the instrument sections; the test involved 50 items about reading comprehension. To ensure the tests were delivered in an identical fashion, the researcher administered the test for each group, giving the same instruction in each case. The researcher administered the pretest to both groups in the same class and recorded the scores, then both groups received instruction through different media for twelve weeks and three hours each week by the same instructor. During the twelve weeks, for classroom practice, TOEFL (2002) were used. The learners instructed by the CALL also used the CD versions of these materials.

2.4. Procedure

The subjects in the experimental group (30 female subjects) worked alone on a computer and learned at their will (all the subjects in the experimental group knew how to use computer). They studied any section as much as they liked.

The researcher did not participate in the teaching/learning process, but the researcher monitored the class just to make sure that subjects were working with the computer and to help if anything went wrong with the computers.

The subjects in the control group (30 female subjects) met the researcher three hours each session during twelve weeks. The same materials (printed and paper version of the practice tests) were used according to the schedule set by the researcher. Subjects studied reading comprehension during three hours. On the last day of classes, the researcher administered the posttest. The scores obtained by the pretest and posttest were statistically analyzed.

2.5. Data Analysis

An independent samples t-test appeared to be an appropriate tool for data analysis in this study since there were two groups who were evaluated through pre and posttests. The interview data were also utilized to shed light on the content analysis.

III. RESULT AND CONCLUSION

3.1. Result

Research Question 1

The main purpose of the present study was to examine the effect of computer-assisted language learning (CALL) on the reading comprehension of expository texts for the Iranian university female senior. A glance at the reading comprehension mean scores probably showed that the experimental group who were benefited from computer performed better, **t-observed = 7.65**, **t-critical = 2.00** so **t-observed > t-critical**. The results of the t-test analysis, which mentioned indicate that the researcher has to reject null hypothesis. The experimental group surpassed the control group. This means that the subjects in the experimental group benefited significantly from the instruction in teaching reading with computer and hence this mode of training was significantly more beneficial than the traditional way of teaching reading (Table II).

TABLE II
 INDEPENDENT SAMPLE T-TEST ANALYSIS OF GAIN SCORE DIFFERENCE IN THE READING
 EXPOSITORY TEXTS

	Group	Number of subjects	Mean	Standard Deviation	Variance	t-observed	t-critical	Degree of freedom
Reading Difference	Control	30	31.43	9.05	82.01	7.65	2.00	58
	Experimental	30	39.16	6.89	47.54			

P-value ≤ 0.05

Research Question 2

After two days following the post-test the subjects in the experimental group-including 30 female subjects-were interviewed one by one so that they could put forward their opinions about the CALL. The interview took place in the Islamic University of Khodabandeh without a time limit. The subjects were interviewed in English. They were asked, “**Did you feel comfortable working with the CALL? Why? / Why not?**” on the whole, the subjects (n = 15) said that they did not feel comfortable working with computers. They claimed that they were not used to having computers as an instructional tool in the learning and teaching process. In addition, they added that although their high school had computers in the laboratory, the administration just covered it to protect it from dust and being broken. They just started to use computers while taking the IT course. On the contrary, the other subjects (n = 15) said that they felt comfortable while working with computer. In addition, two of the subjects mentioned that they were used to having computers in their home or high school. In response to the question, “**Was CALL motivating to you? Why?/Why not?**” 90% of the subjects (n = 27) claimed that they found the CALL motivating. The subjects provided several reasons:

- Studying anything as much as they could.
- Spending more time on the sections they are having difficulty in getting immediate feedback
- Reviewing the material they are studying as much as they liked.

However, three of the subjects (10%) mentioned the necessity of having a teacher in the classroom. They believed that the interaction that the computer provided was artificial and they were sometimes bored with the same feedback style (like “this is wrong, please try again,” etc.).

TABLE III
 FINDING OBTAINED THROUGH THE INTERVIEWS WITH THE PARTICIPANTS (EXPERIMENTAL GROUP=30 FEMALE SUBJECTS)

Questions	frequency		percent	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
1- Feeling comfortable with CALL	15	15	50%	50%
2- CALL offers more motivation than traditional class	27	3	90%	10%

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